

регламенту жизни, придерживаться диетических рекомендаций, контролировать вес и соблюдать ограничение физической нагрузки.

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DATA AVERAGING METHODS DURING THE DRINKING WATER INTEGRAL ASSESSMENT

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Abstract

As a result of the analysis of the practice of drinking water integral assessment in terms of chemical safety indicators, problems were identified regarding the minimum required number of samples, the minimum mandatory list of indicators. Based on the results of laboratory analysis of drinking water quality in some towns in the Leningrad Region, risk values and integral indicators were calculated using 3 methods. According to the authors, the most realistic is the calculation of indicators based on the average values of controlled indicators for the year preceding the calculations and only at the point before being fed into the distribution network (method #3).

Keywords: integral assessment of drinking water, unfavorable organoleptic effects, non-carcinogenic risk, carcinogenic risk, Leningrad region.

Formulation of the problem

Currently, more and more attention is paid to the study of the chemical safety of water from centralized water supply systems [11, p.4; 14, p.108]. According to the Federal Service for Surveillance on Consumer Rights Protection and Human Wellbeing (Rosпотребнадзор), an increased content of chemicals and microbial agents in drinking water leads to more than 1.59 million additional cases of diseases in the population of the Russian Federation. The priority risk factors for the health of the population of the Russian Federation from the use of drinking water include elevated concentrations of chloroform, barium, cadmium, lead, nitrites, nickel, copper, iron, manganese, silicon, ammonia, arsenic, nitrates, sulfates, boron, tetrachlorethylene, strontium, carbon tetrachloride, fluorine [10, p.316].

To analyze the probability of occurrence of adverse effects on human health, to develop management decisions to improve the drinking water quality, a drinking water integral assessment is carried out in terms of chemical safety. Analysis of the practice of applying this methodology [2, p.28; 5, p.359; 6, p. 129; 7, p.432; 8, p.99; 12, p.302; 13, p. 165; 16, p. 489] dictates the need to develop specific approaches to risk assessment with the determination of the minimum required number of analysis, the minimum mandatory list of indicators [15, p.321].

Design organizations are faced with the lack of sufficient data from laboratory studies of water source water quality performed in previous years when choosing a technology for water treatment and purification of drinking water when designing water treatment facilities.

The purpose of the study is to substantiate the optimal and most reliable method for conducting a drinking water integral assessment for the development of management decisions, including when choosing a technology for water treatment and water purification.

Materials and methods. The results of laboratory analysis of the drinking water quality in the centralized water supply systems of the cities of Volkhov, Kirishi, Primorsk, Leningrad Region for 2008-2021 [3] using surface water sources were used in the work. Statistical processing of the results was performed using the MS Excel software package. Risk values for olfactory-reflex effects ($Risk_{or}$), carcinogenic ($Risk_{canc}$) and non-carcinogenic ($Risk_{noncanc}$) risks, integral index (II) according to [9] were calculated. 3 calculation methods were used based on the averaged values of indicators:

method #1 - for the entire observation period from 2008 to 2021 separately at each control point (before entering the distribution network, distribution network);

method #2 - for the entire observation period from 2008 to 2021 in total at all control points of the town;
method #3 - for 2021 only at the point before supply to the distribution network.

For the entire study period, the water treatment technology in all the towns under study did not change, however, some changes were made to the monitoring programs (the list of monitored indicators and the frequency of sampling).

Results and discussion. The water quality in the centralized water supply systems of the towns of Volkhov, Kirishi, Primorsk is monitored monthly at the points of water intake, after water treatment, before being supplied to the distribution network and to the distribution network. Laboratory analysis are carried out on microbiological, parasitological, organoleptic and generalized indicators, inorganic substances and substances that enter and form in the process of water treatment.

To assess the impact on the health of the population, based on the results of laboratory studies of drinking water before being supplied to the distribution network and in the distribution network, an drinking water integral assessment was carried out in terms of chemical safety indicators.

From the list of controlled during 2018-2021. the most significant indicators from the medical and hygienic positions were selected [4]:

- carcinogenic risk according to the non-threshold model – cadmium, arsenic, lead, chloroform, chromium;

- non-carcinogenic risk using a non-threshold method - aluminum, ammonia / ammonium ion (NH_3/NH_4^+), iron, cadmium, manganese, arsenic, petroleum products, nickel, nitrates (NO_3), nitrites (NO_2), lead, fluorine, chloroform, chromium, zinc;

- risk of occurrence of olfactory-reflex effects - pH value, aluminum, ammonia/ammonium ion (NH_3/NH_4^+), iron, smell, manganese, turbidity, sulfates, residual free chlorine, chlorides, color.

To assess the carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic risk at the points of the distribution network, the results of analysis of the relevant indicators were used before entering the network, since in the absence of pollutants entering the process of transporting water through the distribution network, their concentrations remain unchanged [1, p.725].

To compare calculation methods and choose the most realistic one, the results of calculation by method #1 were used only at the point before supply to the distribution network. The results of the integral assessment performed by different calculation methods showed a pronounced variability in the values of all indicators (Table 1).

Table 1.

Results of the drinking water integral assessment supplied to the population of the towns of Volkhov, Kirishi and Primorsk

Title	The value of the risk indicator		
	Volkhov	Kirishi	Primorsk
<i>method #1</i>			
Risk _{or}	1,60	1,90	9,91
Risk _{noncanc}	0,52	0,14	0,23
Risk _{canc}	14,88	6,25	6,05
II	17,00	8,29	16,20
<i>method #2</i>			
Risk _{or}	1,60	0,5	9,79
Risk _{noncanc}	0,12	0,09	0,10
Risk _{canc}	14,98	6,03	4,09
II	16,70	6,63	13,98
<i>method #1</i>			
Risk _{or}	1,60	5,05	0,64
Risk _{noncanc}	0,87	0,25	0,07
Risk _{canc}	6,07	5,68	2,86
II	8,54	10,98	3,57

In the towns of Volkhov and Primorsk, the highest II values were obtained by method #1, in the town of Kirishi - by method #3.

The highest value of the risk of olfactory-reflex effects in the town of Kirishi was obtained using method #3, in the town of Primorsk - method #1, and in the town of Volkhov the values did not differ.

The values of non-carcinogenic risk in the water of the towns of Volkhov and Kirishi reached the highest values using method #3, in the town of Primorsk - method #1.

The highest values of carcinogenic risk in the water of the town of Primorsk were obtained using method #1, the town of Volkhov - methods #1 and #2, the town

of Kirishi practically did not differ, regardless of the method of calculation.

The contribution of individual risk indicators to the II value is also characterized by variability (Fig. 1-3), which may be due to different levels of controlled indicators and a long observation period (methods #1 and #2).

According to the authors, a long observation period increases labor costs for the collection and statistical processing of the results, and does not guarantee the reliability of the calculation results. Method #3 seems to be more realistic, the calculations make it possible to estimate the existing quality of drinking water, which may be improved or worsened compared to previous years.

Fig. 1. The structure of the II for the drinking water quality in the town of Volkhov, taking into account the averaging period

Fig. 2. The structure of the II for the drinking water quality in the town of Kirishi, taking into account the averaging period

Fig. 3. The structure of the II for the drinking water quality in the town of Primorsk, taking into account the averaging period

Conclusions.

1. A drinking water integral assessment in terms of chemical safety indicators can be performed by all proposed methods, however, method #3 is the most realistic.

2. When using methods #1 and #2, the results of the integral assessment may turn out to be unreasonably overestimated or underestimated due to possible changes in monitoring programs over a long period of time, changes in the quality of water sources.

3. The application of method #3 makes it possible to obtain the result of an integrated assessment taking into account the current drinking water quality indicators and to predict the risk values without taking into account the dynamics of indicators for the previous period, thus eliminating the assessment uncertainties.

According to the authors, when developing management decisions to improve water quality, it is sufficient to perform an integral assessment of water before supplying it to the distribution network based on the values of indicators averaged over the previous year (method #3).

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